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Effect of hot isostatic pressing on the microstructure of laser powder bed fused A20X™ alloy

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Abstract. In the present work, an attempt has been made to do a combined hot isostatic pressing (HIP) & solution treatment in a single-step and the effect of different cooling rates (quenching and annealing) on the microstructure was examined. For a comparison, solution treatment (without HIP) was also analysed. It was observed that HIP treatment was successful in reducing the porosities of the L-PBF part. Although, it was not an efficient treatment for the dissolution of the θ -Al₂Cu phase. Furthermore, in both HIP-Quenched and HIP-Annealed treatments a sign of incipient melting was observed along the grain boundaries. Solution treatment without HIP did not show incipient melting.

1. Introduction

A20X™ is a newly developed high strength Al alloy (Al-Cu-Mg-Ag-Ti-B) which has overcome the limitations of hot cracking susceptibility and high fibre-laser reflectivity inherent to the high strength Al alloys thanks to the presence of pre-embedded TiB₂ particles [1]. Being a precipitation hardening alloy, much attention has been given to the post-processing T6 and T7 heat treatments i.e., solution treatment followed by artificial aging [2,3]. The alloy gains its strength by the precipitation of plate-type coherent- Ω and semi-coherent θ' phase during artificial aging. Recently, the response of the alloy towards T4 (natural aging) has also been explored [4].

It was well acknowledged that L-PBF processing of A20X™ alloy induces defects such as lack of fusion or gas induced porosities [5]. Such defects possess a detrimental effect on the mechanical properties, degrading the in-service life of the component. To mitigate such defects, a post-processing treatment of Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) has been found to be highly beneficial [6]. Four primary mechanisms are responsible for a pore elimination through HIP: plastic flow, power-law creep, Coble creep (grain boundary diffusion), and Nabarro–Herring creep (lattice diffusion) [7]. HIP conventionally offers slow cooling rate at the end of the cycle, however, with an integration of a new quenching module called uniform rapid cooling (URC), it is now possible to combine HIP & solution treatment in a single-step to reduce the time and energy of post-processing treatments [8]. HIP of L-PBF A20X™ alloy is still a less touched domain. To the authors' knowledge, till now there has been only one work demonstrating the micro-mechanical response of the HIPed parts [6]. In the present work, an attempt has been made to observe the effect of combined post-processing heat treatment i.e., HIP & solution treatment on the microstructure

developed. At the end of the HIP treatment, two cooling rates have been explored (i) quenching ($\sim 770^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) and (ii) annealing ($\sim 20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$). A comparison has also been made with a non-HIPed solution treatment.

2. Experimental

A commercial gas atomized A20XTM powder was purchased from ECKART GmbH. The powder morphology is shown in figure 1(a). The particle size distribution and nominal chemical composition are presented in reference [3]. L-PBF processing of cubic ($10\times 10\times 10\text{ mm}^3$) samples was performed in an EOS M270 dual mode system by an optimized set of processing parameters as described in our previous work [4]. HIP was performed in a Quintus QIH 15 L equipped with a molybdenum furnace in an inert Ar atmosphere. HIP cycle was comprised of heating from room temperature to 530°C with a $\sim 7^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, holding for 1 h at 530°C under a pressure of 100 MPa followed by (i) quenching and (ii) annealing. Quenching was performed in a uniform rapid cooling (URC) module and annealing was done by a conventional process of furnace cooling ($\sim 20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$). Table 1 presents the nomenclature of various heat-treated conditions. Metallographic sample preparation was performed by grinding with SiC papers up to 4000 grit followed by colloidal silica polishing. Samples were not etched. Microstructure was examined using a Phenom XL table-top scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with secondary electron (SE), back scattered electron (BSE) detectors and an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Porosity content was measured from the SEM-BSE micrographs and analysed by ImageJ software. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed in a Panalytical Empyrean using a monochromatic Cu-K α radiation of 1.54 \AA operated at 40 kV and 40 mA with a step size of 0.013° and 25 s per step. Differential scanning calorimetry was done on the as-built (AB) samples in a NETZSCH 214 Polyma. Samples were heated from 40°C to 570°C and cooled to 40°C at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a N_2 atmosphere.

Figure 1. (a) SEM-SE micrograph of A20XTM alloy powder and (b) schematic of a HIP cycles.

Table 1. Nomenclature of various heat-treated conditions

Heat treatment	Temperature, pressure, and time
ST	530°C for 1 h + Quenched
R-ST	530°C as reached + Quenched
HIP-Q	530°C and 100 MPa for 1 h + Quenched
HIP-An	530°C and 100 MPa for 1 h + Annealed

3 Results

3.1 Macro-porosity

Figure 2 displays the low-magnification SEM-BSE micrographs of the AB and HIPed parts i.e., HIP-Q and HIP-An. Based on the morphology, porosities in the AB state were identified as gas induced porosities (spherical) and lack of fusion (high aspect ratio) (figure 2(a)). Post to the HIP treatment, macro-porosities reduced (figure 2(b) and 2(c)). The porosity content was reduced from AB ($0.23 \pm 0.21\%$) to the HIPed parts (HIP-Q ($0.06 \pm 0.02\%$) and HIP-An ($0.05 \pm 0.03\%$)).

Figure 2. (a) Low-Mag SEM-BSE micrographs of (a) AB, (b) HIP-Q and (c) HIP-An

3.2 Phase and thermal analysis

The DSC profile of the AB state during heating and subsequent cooling is shown in figure 3(a). During heating a broad exothermic peak from 200-360°C was observed. It is a peak representing precipitation of various types of Al_2Cu phase such as Ω , θ' and θ . Precipitation peak was followed by a broad endothermic peak range from 400-530°C, representing the dissolution of all the forms of Al_2Cu [3]. The θ dissolution completes at $\sim 530^\circ\text{C}$ and θ starts to re-precipitate at $\sim 502^\circ\text{C}$ during cooling. The XRD patterns of the HIPed and non-HIPed conditions are shown in figure 3(b). The phases identified were Al, TiB_2 and $\theta\text{-Al}_2\text{Cu}$. In the HIP-Q condition there was still a presence of θ peak. The peak intensity was much higher in the case of HIP-An. Whereas no peak was observed in the non-HIPed conditions i.e., ST and R-ST (see inset figure 3(b')).

Figure 3. (a) DSC profile of AB condition, (b) XRD whole line profiles and (b') individual peak of $\theta\text{-Al}_2\text{Cu}$ {110} of HIPed and non-HIPed conditions.

3.3 Microstructure

Figure 4 shows the SEM-BSE micrographs of the AB, ST, HIP-Q and HIP-An conditions. The AB state showed a typical fine cellular microstructure with eutectic- θ as cell boundaries (figure 4(a)). In ST, the cellular microstructure vanished (figure 4(b)). Cellular microstructure also vanished after HIP-Q treatment, although, grain boundaries and grain triple junctions were decorated by fine precipitates (figure 4(c)). These precipitates are likely to be of an equilibrium θ phase.

Figure 4. SEM-BSE micrograph of (a) AB, (b) ST, (c) HIP-Q and (d) HIP-An (yellow arrow showing incipient melted region and purple arrow showing spheroidal blocky- θ inside grains).

Figure 5. SEM-BSE micrograph of HIPed LPBF A20X™ alloy showing the EDS mapping on the selected region of incipient melting (a and b) and elemental line scan across a grain boundary precipitate (orange arrow) (a' and b') in (a-a') HIP-Q and (b-b') HIP-An sample.

In an HIP-An state, coarser θ precipitates were present (figure 4(d)). This observation was also supported by the XRD spectrum, see figure 3(b'). Surprisingly, in both the HIP-Q and HIP-An conditions, grain boundaries were also accompanied by elongated pores and in certain boundaries there were discontinuous pores (figure 4(c) and 4(d)). By looking at the morphology of these porosities, they are resembling of an incipient melting and not of cracks generated by decohesion during plastic deformation. Incipient melting is a localized melting of secondary phases primarily located at the grain boundaries [9]. Such porosities due to incipient melting was not observed in ST. The elemental mapping around the incipient melted region and line scan across

the grain boundary precipitate (GBP) of the HIPed samples is presented in figure 5. In both the HIP-Q and HIP-An conditions, it was observed that GBPs are Cu-rich (figure 5(a) and 5(b)). The same was also suggested by the line scan across the precipitate (figure 5(a') and 5(b')). The concentration profile of other solutes (Ag and Mg) remains more or less the same. This indicates that these GBPs in the HIPed conditions are only of an equilibrium θ -Al₂Cu phase. It was also revealed that the grain boundary pores were accompanied by fine particles of TiB₂.

4 Discussion

4.1 Incomplete dissolution

An incomplete dissolution of θ was witnessed in HIP-Q. Whereas a more complete dissolution was observed in the non-HIPed solution treatments performed at the same temperature i.e., ST (figure 3(b')). Interestingly, no θ peak was observed even in R-ST, indicating that most of the θ phase has been dissolved during the ramping stage itself. It was speculated that the incomplete dissolution in the HIP-Q was associated to diffusional creep that assists in the densification during HIP. During diffusional creep, solute atoms migrate along the grain boundaries (Coble creep) and towards the grain boundaries through lattice diffusion (Nabarro-Herring creep) [10]. Thus, the presence of θ phase along grain boundaries is likely to be a result of a precipitation by diffusional creep during densification. These GBPs are of blocky- θ phase and possess much slower dissolution characteristics [11]. In the case of ST and R-ST, during ramping the eutectic- θ cell boundaries initially breakdown into fine spheroidal particles and hence would accelerate the dissolution. Thus, in a ST and R-ST condition, the finer spheroidal eutectic- θ dissolves rather than forming blocky- θ . A more detailed analysis of the θ dissolution was reported in our previous work [3]. In HIP-An, the blocky- θ phase re-precipitated and coarsened due to much slower cooling rate (figure 4(d) and 5(b)).

4.2 Incipient melting

The HIPed samples (HIP-Q and HIP-An) showed the sign of incipient melting along grain boundaries (figure 5). Whereas no incipient melting was observed in non-HIPed conditions. The spheroidal blocky- θ present inside the grains in both HIPed and non-HIPed conditions doesn't melt (figure 4). We suspect that there could be two possible reasons for the formation of incipient melting in an A20XTM alloy:

- (i) Deformation/strain induced GBPs of low-melting phases such as S-Al₂CuMg and Q-Al₇Cu₃Mg₆
- (ii) Morphology assisted pre-melting of a grain boundary θ -Al₂Cu precipitate.

The melting point of S-Al₂CuMg and Q-Al₇Cu₃Mg₆ is 495°C and 513°C, respectively, which is much lower than the solutioning temperature (530°C). However, we did not find these phases either by XRD (figure 3(b)), or in the EDS (figure 5(a') and 5(b')). The EDS line scan across GBPs showed only Cu segregation. Thus, we suspect that the incipient melting was due to the morphology assisted pre-melting of θ -Al₂Cu. The melting point of a θ phase is influenced by its morphology [9]. The higher interfacial area of the elongated θ GBPs would favour pre-melting with respect to the spheroidal θ phase present inside the grains.

5 Conclusion

Microstructure of the L-PBF A20XTM alloy was investigated in two HIPed treatments (i) quenched (HIP-Q) and (ii) annealed (HIP-An). The conclusions drawn are the following: (i) Macro-porosity

was reduced after the HIP treatment, (ii) HIP treatment was inefficient to dissolve θ -Al₂Cu, whereas solution treatment without HIP was more efficient, (iii) in HIP-Q sample, θ phase was precipitated along the grain boundaries, whereas coarser θ phase was observed in HIP-An, and (iv) incipient melting along grain boundaries was observed in the HIPed samples. Morphological assisted pre-melting of grain boundary θ -Al₂Cu phase could be the possible reason. An optimized HIP & solution treatment parameters (temperature, pressure and cooling rate) should be further investigated to get a desirable microstructure i.e., no incipient melting and a more complete dissolution of θ -Al₂Cu.

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